

The future of museums. An analysis from the visitors' perspective in the Spanish context

The social role of museums has long been part of the academic debate: different disciplines and fields of knowledge have explored the social shift of museums and have re-envisioned their future. However, little attention has been paid to the views of visitors on the future of museums.

This article addresses this issue by adopting an audience development approach. It analyses a questionnaire administered to 685 visitors to 16 Spanish museums between October and December 2019. The findings revealed that the audience believed that museums should offer a vision that respects cultural diversity, and provide enriching and memorable experiences, while at the same time defending the classic values of cultural heritage, among others. Women and visitors that gave more importance to the practice of visiting museums than to other cultural practices were found to be the most demanding visitor segments.

Keywords: audience development; visitor studies; visitor perception; museum studies; museum changes

Word count: 6,039 words (including title, abstract, keywords, main text and bibliography)

1. Introduction

Museums, and specially their social role, have long been part of a vibrant debate involving many different fields of knowledge, such as museology, arts management, cultural policy, sociology or leisure studies, among others (Ayala, Cuenca-Amigo and Cuenca 2020a). The debate has not been free from extreme positions. In the early 20th century, for instance, Italian futurists criticized museums and condemned them to disappearance for representing the authority of the past (Marinetti 1909). This argument

was also used by sociologists such as Bourdieu and Darbel (1969), and by postmodern philosophers such as Lyotard (1987). However, there have also been several voices advocating for their existence, both in Spain and internationally, including for example Ovejero (1934) and Coleman, through the American Association of Museums (1927), respectively. Both Ovejero and Coleman defended the educational task of museums and the need for them to incorporate discourses that are closer to society. These approaches eventually materialised in the postulates of the New Museology (Rivière 1985).

The debate is far from over and has raised many new questions in recent years. The field of museology (Hernández 2006; Mairesse 2017) and that of visitor studies (Falk and Dierking 2012; Pérez Santos 2018) continue to study the social role of museums and the need to work on the improvement of their relationship with audiences basing on collected evidence. From a more general approach, also, leisure studies are concerned with the visitor's aesthetic leisure experience (Amigo and Cuenca-Amigo 2017; Csikszentmihalyi and Robinson 1990) and cultural management highlights the need of museums to increase their audience development initiatives (Black 2012; Righolt 2013). In view of all this, how do visitors envision the museum of the future? What changes should museums undertake? And which segments of the public are the most demanding in relation to the implementation of these changes? In order to answer these questions, this study uses a theoretical framework that reflects on the shift of museums towards society according to different theoretical approaches. The main contributions of the study will then be presented, namely the results from the analysis of the questionnaire carried out on 685 visitors to 16 Spanish museums, and the discussion of the main points arising from it. Finally, some concluding remarks will be offered.

2. Theoretical framework

The tasks of museums and the need to strengthen their social approach has been discussed in academia for more than a hundred years. Bearing this in mind, this theoretical framework examines two separate approaches: (1) an audience development approach, a management process that is currently used to tackle the social challenges faced by museums; and (2) the various perspectives adopted prior to audience development by other disciplines to address some of those social challenges.

2.1. An Audience Development Approach

Audience development is a visitor-centered management process that is currently used in museums. Some authors have interpreted it as a need to focus on the audience and place this above an emphasis on heritage (Díaz 2008), although this has been somewhat controversial (Velázquez 2017). However, audience development does not have to come at the expense of the artistic dimension. On the contrary, it contemplates both the social approach and the programming of exhibitions and collections. According to Rogers (1998), audience development is the intersection of programming, marketing, and education. This perspective is supported and reinforced by the study carried out by Bollo, Da Milano, Gariboldi, and Torch (2017), which established programming as one of the eight strategic areas of intervention for audience development in cultural organizations, along with participation and co-creation; digital environments; use of data; place, collaboration and institutional relations; organizational change; and capacity building.

The current turbulent, ever-changing and increasingly technological context poses various new challenges for museums. Black (2012) argued that these challenges can be grouped into two main thematic areas: the need to increase and diversify funding; and the

link between museums and their communities. Both areas were also identified in the Spanish context by Ayala, Cuenca-Amigo and Cuenca (2019).

As a starting point, it should be stated that audience development is not a scientific discipline, but a management approach within cultural institutions. There are several definitions of this term, shaped in different countries based on their specific contexts (Cuenca-Amigo and Makua 2017).

Jancovich (2015) claimed that the application of audience development to museums has two complementary dimensions: (1) the general management perspective, which implies a global change of these institutions to become more visitor-centered; and (2) the heterogeneous vision focused on specific areas linked to audience development. According to the systematic literature review carried out by Ayala, Cuenca-Amigo, and Cuenca (2020a), these specific areas are: community outreach; participation; visitor studies; communication; marketing; education; technology and digital environments; and the professional profile of staff.

In Europe, the relevance of this topic is highlighted by several statements of the European Commission who considered audience development to be a priority within the Creative Europe Culture Sub-Programme 2014-2020 (European Parliament 2013) and has recently created the cluster “Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society” among the global challenges to be tackled under the Horizon Europe Programme 2021.2027. Therefore, it is relevant to consider the definition of audience development offered by the European Commission: ‘Audience development is a strategic, dynamic and interactive process of making the arts widely accessible. It aims at engaging individuals and communities in experiencing, enjoying, participating in and valuing the arts through various means available today for cultural operators, from digital tools to volunteering, from co-creation to

partnerships. Audience development can be understood in various ways, depending on its objectives and target groups:

- increasing audiences (attracting audiences with the same socio-demographic profile as the current audience);
- deepening relationship with the audiences (enhancing the experience of the current audiences in relation to a cultural event and/or encouraging them to discover related or even non-related, more complex art forms, thus fostering loyalty and return visits);
- diversifying audiences (attracting people with a different socio-demographic profile to the current audiences, including people with no previous contact with the arts)'.
(European Commission, 2012, 5)

Thus, audience development places visitors at the heart of cultural organizations and adopts a multidisciplinary perspective. It is a tool for museums and other cultural institutions to implement the theoretical tenets of different disciplines, which will be examined in the next section.

2.2. Claiming the Social Role of Museums: a Brief Overview of Different Disciplinary Perspectives

Two general groups of scientific disciplines have focused on the relationship between museums and society: museology and its variants; and museum-focused sociological studies. In the field of museology, there are two main theories: New Museology (Hernández 2006; Mairesse 2017; Rivière 1985; Vergo 1989) or Social Museology (Navajas and González 2018; Lavado Paradinas 2015), and Critical Museology (Lorente 2012, 2015; Santacana and Hernández 2006; Shelton 2013). These theories have defended the need to place the public at the center of cultural organizations and to work towards improving the relationship between museums and their communities. They have also questioned the unique hegemonic discourses in museums, which often fail to reflect

diverse communities and different sensitivities (Vergo 1989; Díaz 2008), and emphasize the need to become more inclusive and diversity-sensitive spaces (Sandell 2002, 1998).

It is also important to highlight visitor studies and the assessments of exhibitions, which are essential for the understanding of visitors' socio-demographic and cultural profile, attitudes and interests, opinions, experiences and perceived barriers (Falk and Dierking 2012; Hooper-Greenhill 2006; Pérez Castellanos 2016, 2019; Pérez Santos 2018). All these studies can be carried out before, after and during museum visits to obtain a more comprehensive picture (Davidson 2017), as they provide professionals with data with which to enhance the impact of museums on their audience and their communities (Colomer 2013; Tomlinson and Roberts 2011).

Sociological studies in this area notably include the theories of Cultural Democratization and Cultural Democracy, (Hadley and Belfiore 2018). In general terms, these tenets are the background to the audience development approach (Cuenca-Amigo 2014). Cultural Democratization advocates opening institutions to everyone, while Cultural Democracy promotes accessibility, cultural diversity, and social participation in institutions (Bonet and Négrier 2019; Pinochet and Güell 2018). From a more radical point of view, Kelly (1984) has argued that Cultural Democracy was originally a revolution against the pre-established order. In turn, this approach may be related to the post-modern ideals mentioned above. It criticizes the hegemonic tradition of single discourses and defends the need to conceive culture as a process that emerges from society, where audience participation is encouraged at different levels of management: from guiding cultural visits to getting involved in decision-making and the management of organizations (Brown, Novak-Leonard, and Gilbride 2011; McCarthy and Jinnett 2001; Simon 2010).

In the last decades, feminism and gender studies have growingly succeed to introduce a gender perspective in the discussions on the role of museums around the world (Bergsdóttir 2016). As spaces for social communication and the defense of historical values, museums need to make the role of women throughout History and their contributions to cultural heritage visible, as advocated by Izquierdo, López and Prados (2012). Even if this process is still in its incipient stages in Spain, the gender perspective has started to bring about some relevant changes in the programming of very prestigious and influential institutions, as the recent exhibition *Invitadas (Uninvited Guests)* at the Museo del Prado shows. Leisure Studies consider visitors' leisure experience and make a claim for the social mission of museums on that basis. Given that visitors' experiences are subjective and depend on multiple factors, museums' may not be in a position to guarantee that their social goals will be fulfilled (Monteagudo and San Salvador del Valle 2017). However, they can attempt to provide valuable leisure experiences (Cuenca 2014) by taking into account different dimensions, such as aesthetics (Amigo 2014; Amigo and Cuenca-Amigo 2017), education (Hanquinet and Savage 2012) and entertainment (Clair 2011).

3. Methodology

This section outlines the design of the questionnaire used as a data collection instrument, the sample selection and description, and the various data collection processes involved.

3.1. Questionnaire design

The questionnaire was designed by the project's team. It was based on a pre-test carried out on a sample of 75 people: 42 women and 33 men, not included in the subsequent

analysis (Ayala, Cuenca-Amigo and Cuenca 2020b). After this first phase, the instrument was restructured and expanded until the final version of the questionnaire was devised.

Although the questionnaire covered numerous aspects related to audience perception, this study focuses on the answers to question seven, namely, ‘To what extent do you think museums should:

- Become places of leisure and enjoyment
- Provide enriching and memorable experiences
- Offer a vision that respects cultural diversity
- Defend the classic values of cultural heritage
- Preserve heritage rather than exhibiting it
- Include the gender perspective in their activities
- Become spaces for the social inclusion of people with any kind of disability
- Carry out programs that increase citizens’ social welfare
- Increase the number of visitors to reach more people
- Compensate for education and knowledge that audiences may not possess?’

Given the innovative nature of the study, there were no previously validated scales, so the question was constructed *ad hoc* for this study based on the literature review. Some of the references used as a basis for the scale items are outlined below.

In the context of the social shift in focus on museum audiences and on visitors’ perceptions of the changes that should be made, it is worth noting the role of museums as leisure spaces (Amigo 2014), capable of generating enriching experiences (Cuenca 2014; Monteagudo and San Salvador del Valle 2017), even though the audience does not always perceive them in this way (Hanquinet and Savage 2012). Moreover, theories such as Cultural Democracy (Bonet and Négrier 2019; Hadley and Belfiore 2018; Pinochet and

Güell 2018) and New Museology (Hernández 2006; Vergo 1989) claim the need for museums to embrace cultural diversity, the social inclusion of different groups (Cho and Jolley 2016; Roque 2014), and the gender perspective (Bergsdóttir 2016; Izquierdo, López and Prados 2012). All of this should be incorporated while also keeping the balance between preserving heritage and defending traditional heritage values (Mavrin and Glavas, 2014; Strachan and Mackay 2013; Velázquez 2017).

Another significant aspect of the study is the audience perception of museums' ability to make an impact on social welfare (Museums Association 2017; Gayle 2015). In addition, in line with an audience development approach, it is important to consider some visitors' desire to increase their participation (Brown, Novak-Leonard, and Gilbride 2011; Simon 2010); their opinion on the pedagogical role of museums (Fernández Bravo 2016; Hanquinet and Savage 2012); and whether they believe it is necessary for museums to engage in outreach and increase their number of visitors.

The response choices for the 11 items were designed in the form of a five-point Likert scale. In this ordinal-type scale, each subject has five different response choices for each of the items, and a sixth option not to answer (Don't know/Not applicable). The options included in the scale were: (1) Strongly Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Neither Agree nor Disagree, (4) Agree, and (5) Strongly Agree. The choice of this type of scale by the research team was due to its efficiency, despite having been developed some time ago (Elejabarrieta and Iñiguez 2008; Méndez and Peña 2007).

To enhance the analysis, the responses to the question about changes were cross-referenced with three independent variables from the questionnaire: gender, age and the importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices. For this last variable, the response options were set out as a five-point Likert scale in the questionnaire,

and for the analysis they were divided into three groups: (1) No importance or less importance, (3) The same importance, and (4) A lot or much more importance.

3.2. Sample Selection and Data Collection

Non-probability convenience sampling of people who attended the selected museums was used. A total of 685 valid questionnaires were completed, yielding a maximum error of 3.7% at a 95% confidence level, calculated for infinite samples. When the data were analyzed, 4.2% of the questionnaires (completed by 30 individuals) were discarded either because they provided incomplete data, had been completed by people under 18 years of age (which is the legal age in Spain), or the interviewees had not signed the informed consent form that contains the researchers' commitment to an ethical processing of data.

The recruitment of participants took place as they were leaving the museums. This occurred from 15 October to 17 December 2019, from Monday to Sunday both in the morning and in the afternoon. The average time taken to answer the questionnaire was 20 minutes. The questionnaires were administered in the Spanish language in paper form. The museums in Bilbao and Barcelona also provided questionnaires in Basque and Catalan, respectively (co-official languages in those regions). Finally, when the participants' attention was drawn to the questionnaire, the process included explaining the questionnaire's characteristics, format, and the data privacy policy. They were advised that they could withdraw from the survey at any point. Participants were also asked to sign an informed consent form to allow for their data to be analyzed on an aggregate basis.

Of the 16 museums selected for the sample, 11 were part of the General Subdirectorate of State Museums in Spain. The rest were: the Museum of Fine Arts, and the Guggenheim Museum, both located in Bilbao; the Catalanian Museum of

Contemporary Art (MACBA); the Catalanian National Art Museum (MNAC); and the Lázaro Galdiano Museum. Table 1 shows the name and location of the museums, the number of questionnaires obtained from each, and the category to which they belong according to the General Directory of Museums and Collections in Spain, which falls under the Ministry of Culture and Sport. The selection of these museums corresponds to the aims of the research project to which this study belongs.

[Table 1. Museum selection and sampling]

Data analysis was performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics package (version 26). In order to calculate the mean shown in Table 3, each of the answer options was translated into a numerical option from 1 to 5 for ease of data handling, where 1 was Strongly Disagree and 5 was Strongly Agree. The sixth option, which indicated no answer was provided, was excluded from the analysis.

To carry out the analysis of the selected question with each of the chosen independent variables, one-factor ANOVAs were performed. The reason for this choice instead of a factorial ANOVA combining all the variables was the degree of dependence between the independent variables analyzed. Pearson's correlation was significant for the relationship between age and the importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices ($r=0.121$).

The data obtained through the one-factor ANOVA analysis showed where the difference in means between the sample groups (the variables) and each of the items in the question was significant. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. When this happened, eta-squared was also calculated to indicate effect size through the ANOVA (η^2 around 0.01 = small effect; η^2 around 0.06 = medium effect; η^2 around 0.14 = large effect).

3.3. Description of the Sample

The sample was composed of 685 individuals who completed the questionnaire in its entirety. Table 2 shows the classification of the individuals according to each of the independent variables analyzed.

[Table 2. Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample]

4. Results analysis and discussion

Firstly, this section presents an overview of the scores obtained for each individual item. Table 3 displays the items in descending order according to the mean of the responses on each of them. This enabled the analysis of which changes were demanded as well as their intensity. There were six items with an average that was higher than 4 points: (1) Offer a vision that respects cultural diversity, (2) Provide enriching and memorable experiences, (3) Defend the classic values of cultural heritage, (4) Compensate for the education and knowledge that the public may not possess, (5) Become spaces for the social inclusion of people with any kind of disability, and (6) Carrying out programmes to increase the social welfare of citizens.

[Table 3. Results of the measures of each item for the question analyzed]

The analysis of these results reflects how the public continues to demand that museums should become more involved in society. In other words, audiences want museums to continue to face social challenges (Ayala, Cuenca-Amigo and Cuenca 2019; Black 2012).

The least demanded action was ‘Become places of leisure and enjoyment’. A potential explanation for this result is that leisure is often perceived negatively. For instance, for older generations, for whom the positive dominant values were linked to work, leisure tends to be associated with ideas such as idleness or laziness. Additionally, in the specific case of museums, people tend to see the relationship between museums and leisure as being frivolous (Cuenca 2004; 2018). However, transforming museums into more leisure-focused organizations does not have to mean turning museums into mere theme parks and disregarding their traditional functions (Zbucheá 2015). While this change could contribute to the enhancement and promotion of enjoyment, knowledge, and aesthetic experiences (Amigo 2014; Cuenca 2014; Novillo et al. 2018), this was not clearly perceived by audiences.

In addition, the analysis of the item ‘Defend the classical values of cultural heritage’, showed that the public also demanded that museums should continue to maintain a balance between social transformations and the defense of their traditional functions, as some scientific theories have held (Mavrin and Glavas 2014; Strachan and Mackay 2013; Velázquez 2017).

Secondly, having analyzed the general opinion on which changes were demanded to a greater or lesser extent, it is worth turning to the data, taking into account the three independent variables: gender, age and the importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices.

4.2.1. Gender

Table 4 shows the significant results ($p < 0.05$) obtained in the one-factor ANOVA analysis by cross-referencing each of the demanded changes with the gender variable.

[Table 4. ANOVA results of items that were significant when cross-referencing the gender variable and demanded changes]

The results shown in Table 5 show how women perceived more changes than men did in all five cases. Non-binary persons represented 0.4% of the total sample (3 individuals). Therefore, due to the lack of representativeness, no further analysis was carried out.

[Table 5. Relative frequencies of responses for items that were significant when the gender variable was cross-referenced with demanded actions]

In the Spanish context, according to the Survey on Cultural Habits and Practices (2018-2019) the percentage of women who visit museums is higher than that of men. In addition, the Permanent Laboratory of Museum Audiences of Spain (Laboratorio Permanente de Públicos 2017) hold that women show more initiative in the decision to visit museums as a family. Therefore, taking into account the results of this study, women's influence and initiative lead them to demand more changes than men. For example, the second greatest difference between gender groups was found for the item linked to the inclusion of people with disabilities in museums had. Some 81% of women were in favor of this change in contrast to 69% of men.

The biggest difference between the two groups was seen in the gender perspective item, where 29% of women were totally in favor of this change compared to 18% of men. The reason for this difference lies in the fact that the gender perspective is a transformation demanded by the feminist movements as opposed to the traditionally masculine vision (Beauvoir 1987; Bergsdóttir 2016). In other words, since women are

demanding equality with men, it makes sense that they should be the ones to value change more highly (Pampel 2011).

4.2.2. Age

Table 6 shows the significant results ($p < 0.05$) obtained in 4 of the 11 items in the one-factor ANOVA analysis by cross-referencing each of the demanded changes with the age variable.

[Table 6. ANOVA results of items that were significant when cross-referencing the age variable with demanded changes]

Table 7 shows the relative frequencies of the responses to the items that were statistically significant.

[Table 2. Relative frequencies of responses for items that were significant when cross-referencing the age variable with demanded changes]

The item with the greatest difference between the age groups was the one linked to gender. As age increased, the total percentage in favor of this transformation decreased. Compared to 64% of young people, 46% of those over 65 years of age demanded this change. This may be due to this movement has become stronger in recent years; young people are more sensitive to its implementation (Cichy, Lefkowitz, and Fingerma 2007). Moreover, it is interesting to note that it was the over-65 group who most favored increasing the number of visitors, as opposed to younger people, who were the least in favor and most against the item related to taking action on the gender perspective.

The third item that showed differences between the age groups was the one related to leisure. Both young people under 30 and adults between 30 and 45 years of age were in favor of museums promoting experiences linked to leisure, with values of around 43%

both of them. In contrast, 42% of those over 65 were against this change to a certain extent. However, in the next significant item linked to classic heritage values, these scores were reversed. While almost 86% of those over 46 and 65 years of age defended these values, the percentage dropped significantly in the younger groups. The under-30s were most opposed to this change. In other words, when looking at older and younger generations, two poles can be identified relating to the perceived value of leisure (negative vs. positive) and the museums' mission (tradition vs. innovation) (Cuenca 2004; 2018; Maricchiolo, 2016).

4.2.3. Importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices

Table 8 shows that 5 of the 11 items had significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices variable.

[Table 8. ANOVA results of items that were significant when cross-referencing the importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices variable and demanded changes]

Table 9 shows how the participants who gave more importance to the practice of visiting museums compared to other cultural practices were those most in favor of encouraging the changes related to the items that proved to be statistically significant. For example, considering the item about increasing the number of visitors, only 27% of the respondents who believed that visiting museums was not important or had little importance compared to other cultural practices agreed or totally agreed with this statement, whereas this percentage rose to 56% in the case of those who gave a lot or much more importance to visiting museums.

[Table 9. Relative frequencies of responses for items that were significant when the importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices variable was cross-referenced with demanded changes]

This may have been because the importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices was related to the frequency of visits to museums (chi-square = 0.000). This last group was the one that visited museums the most, that is, the people who benefited the most from this type of leisure experience (Amigo 2014). Furthermore, as Hanquinet and Savage (2012) concluded, cultural practices also influence the perception of museums. Therefore, they considered it necessary to extend the positive impact of museums to the rest of society (Gayle 2015). This also explains why this group were most in favor of accessibility for people with some kind of disability and of demanding that museums provide enriching and memorable experiences.

Nevertheless, those who most strongly supported museums were also those who most strongly believed that museums should continue to uphold classic heritage values. In other words, for this group, museums must adapt to society without losing their traditional functions (Mavrin and Glavas 2014; Strachan and Mackay 2013).

5. Final reflection

To conclude, one of the major implications of this research is to highlight the relevance of the audience development approach and its application in the context of the museums sector, as well as the need to continue to explore these aspects in greater depth. Although different schools of thought have claimed since the early 20th century the need of museums to enhance their relationship with society and much has been undertaken in this

direction, this research confirms that there is still room for improvement as visitors continue to demand from them further social changes.

Regarding the social transformations demanded by the audience, it should be noted that of the 11 items proposed in this study, 10 had an average score of more than 3.5; in other words, visitors supported 10 of the 11 proposed actions and changes. Of these items, 6 had an average score of more than 4 out of 5: (1) offer a vision that respects cultural diversity; (2) provide enriching and memorable experiences; (3) defend the classic values of cultural heritage; (4) compensate for the education and knowledge that the public may not possess, (5) become spaces for the social inclusion of people with any kind of disability; and (6) carry out programmes to increase the social welfare of citizens.

A more detailed analysis confirmed which segments of the audience were more demanding in the implementation of these changes. Both women and those who gave more importance to the practice of visiting museums demanded more changes. There was greater heterogeneity with respect to age.

The only item that was not supported was linked to museums as places of leisure. Nevertheless, visitors were keen on the idea that museums should promote memorable and educational experiences, and, from a leisure studies' perspective, this was clearly linked to the idea of creative leisure (Amigo 2014; Cuenca 2014; Novillo et al. 2018).

Although the analysis revealed that there was social support for these changes, it also showed how the participants in the study defended the traditional cultural value of museums. In other terms, they argued for the transformation of museums, but they did not want their purpose and traditional functions to be altered. Therefore, another implication of the study is the defence by visitors of the traditional functions of museums as they transform themselves into institutions more closely linked to society and sensitive

to contemporary issues such as gender, social inclusion and diversity. In short, museums must find ways to preserve their essence while deepening their social role, through the potentialities that audience development offers them.

Even though this study provides results for the Spanish context, these conclusions are also relevant in other contexts. Although other countries may be at a more advanced stage in relation to the implementation of a richer social role of museums, the large amount of research on audience development in museums leads us to believe that this is an ongoing discussion in museums all over the world (Ayala, Cuenca-Amigo and Cuenca 2020a). Nevertheless, it would be interesting to administer the questionnaire used for this research in other geographical contexts and compare the results. This could constitute a future line of research.

Declaration of interest statement:

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Appendix of tables:

Table 1. Museum selection and sampling

Museum name	Location	Category	Sampling dates	N° of questionnaires	% they represent
Sorolla Museum	Madrid	House-Museum	2019/10/15-19	98	14.3%
National Archaeological Museum (MAN)	Madrid	Archaeology	2019/10/15-19	88	12.8%
Museum of Fine Arts of Bilbao	Bilbao	Fine Arts	2019/11/22-24	82	12%
National Sculpture Museum	Valladolid	Fine Arts	2019/10/31 2019/11/01	78	11.4%
MNAC	Barcelona	Fine Arts	2019/11/28-30	63	9.2%
Guggenheim Museum	Bilbao	Contemporary Art	2019/11/30 2019/12/17	47	6.9%
Romanticism Museum	Madrid	Specialized	2019/10/15-19	47	6.9%
MACBA	Barcelona	Contemporary Art	2019/11/28-30	33	4.8%
National Museum of Sub-aquatic Archaeology (ARQVA)	Cartagena	Archaeology	2019/11/30 2019/12/13	29	4.2%
National Museum of Ceramics and Sumptuary Arts 'González Martí'	Valencia	Decorative Arts	2019/11/15-16	26	3.8%
National Museum and Research Centre of Altamira	Santillana del Mar	Archaeology	2019/11/23	22	3.2%
National Museum of Anthropology	Madrid	Ethnographic-Anthropological	2019/10/15-19	19	2.8%
Lázaro Galdiano Museum	Madrid	Fine Arts	2019/10/15-19	16	2.3%
Cerralbo Museum	Madrid	House-Museum	2019/10/15-19	16	2.3%
Museum of America	Madrid	Ethnographic-Anthropological	2019/10/15-19	11	1.6%
National Museum of Decorative Arts	Madrid	Decorative Arts	2019/10/15-19	10	1.5%
Total				685	100%

Source: Own elaboration

Table 2. Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample

Independent variable	Group	Absolute Frequencies	Relative Frequencies
Gender	Women	403	58.8%
	Men	278	40.6%
	Non-binary	3	0.4%
Age	Young 18-29	154	22.5%
	Adults 30-45	134	19.6%
	Adults 46-64	236	34.5%
	Elderly 65 or more	153	22.3%
Importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices	None or less importance	26	3.8%
	The same importance	197	28.8%
	A lot or much more importance	454	66.3%

Source: Own elaboration

Table 3. Results of the measures of each item of the question analyzed

	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree	Mean
Offering a vision that respects cultural diversity	0.9%	1.0%	6.0%	33.4%	56.2%	4.47
Providing enriching and memorable experiences	0.6%	0.7%	5.5%	45.7%	45.8%	4.38
Defending the classic values of cultural heritage	0.7%	3.1%	11.4%	28.6%	53.0%	4.34
Compensating for the education and knowledge that audiences do not possess	1.3%	3.1%	10.7%	39.7%	41.8%	4.22
Becoming places for the social inclusion of people with any kind of disability	1.2%	2.3%	16.1%	36.1%	39.9%	4.16
Carrying out programmes to increase the social welfare of citizens	1.3%	4.4%	17.2%	39.0%	31.5%	4.02
Including the gender perspective in their activities	4.4%	5.8%	25.3%	29.8%	24.2%	3.71
Preserving heritage rather than exhibit it	4.7%	13.9%	21.3%	26.3%	29.6%	3.65
Involving the audience more in the creation of exhibitions	2.6%	7.9%	29.8%	31.8%	20.4%	3.64
Increasing the number of visitors to reach more people	4.4%	10.2%	29.1%	32.0%	19.3%	3.54
Becoming places of leisure that enhance enjoyment	11.1%	20.4%	26.7%	25.5%	10.7%	3.04

Source: Own elaboration

Table 4. ANOVA results of items with significance in crossing the gender variable and changes demanded

		Sum of Squares	df¹	Mean Square	F²	p³	η²⁴
Including the gender perspective in their activities	Between groups	16.715	2	8.357	7.276	0.001	0.023
	Within groups	699.514	609	1.149			
	Total	716.229	611				
Becoming places for the social inclusion of people with any kind of disability	Between groups	16.059	2	8.030	10.767	0.000	0.032
	Within groups	484.734	650	0.746			
	Total	500.793	652				
Carrying out programmes to increase the social welfare of citizens.	Between groups	11.042	2	5.521	6.717	0.001	0.021
	Within groups	522.801	636	0.822			
	Total	533.844	638				
Offering a vision that respects cultural diversity	Between groups	7.941	2	3.971	7.446	0.001	0.022
	Within groups	354.050	664	0.533			
	Total	361.991	666				
Providing enriching and memorable experiences	Between groups	5.920	2	2.960	6.482	0.002	0.019
	Within groups	305.970	670	0.457			
	Total	311.890	672				

Source: Own elaboration

¹ df = degrees of freedom

² F = estimate of the population variance based on the existing variability between means of each group

³ p = Significance (P = o < 0.05)

⁴ η² = *Eta square* (effect size: 0.01 small, 0.06 medium, 0.14 big)

Table 5. Relative frequencies of responses for items with significance in the gender variable

Including the gender perspective in their activities					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
Women	3.23%	5.46%	22.08%	29.78%	28.78%
Men	6.12%	6.47%	30.22%	29.14%	17.63%
Non-binary	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%

Becoming places for the social inclusion of people with any kind of disability					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
Women	0.50%	1.99%	12.66%	34.49%	46.15%
Men	2.16%	2.88%	20.86%	38.49%	30.58%
Non-binary	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	33.33%	33.33%

Carrying out programmes to increase the social welfare of citizens					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
Women	0.50%	2.98%	15.14%	39.21%	34.00%
Men	2.52%	6.47%	20.14%	39.21%	27.34%
Non-binary	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	66.67%

Offering a vision that respects cultural diversity					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
Women	0.74%	0.74%	3.97%	30.77%	61.29%
Men	1.08%	1.44%	8.99%	37.77%	48.20%
Non-binary	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%

Providing enriching and memorable experiences					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
Women	0.74%	0.00%	4.22%	42.68%	50.87%
Men	0.36%	1.80%	7.55%	50.36%	38.13%
Non-binary	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	66.67%

Source: Own elaboration

Table 6. ANOVA results of items with significance in crossing the age variable and changes demanded

		Sum of Squares	df⁵	Mean Square	F⁶	p⁷	η^{28}
Including the gender perspective in their activities	Between groups	12.147	3	4.049	3.516	0.015	0.017
	Within groups	694.400	603	1.152			
	Total	706.547	606				
Increasing the number of visitors to reach more people	Between groups	19.099	3	6.366	5.652	0.001	0.026
	Within groups	720.852	640	1.126			
	Total	739.950	643				
Becoming places of leisure that enhance enjoyment	Between groups	38.827	3	12.942	9.619	0.000	0.043
	Within groups	857.036	637	1.345			
	Total	895.863	640				
Defending the classic values of cultural heritage	Between groups	14.346	3	4.782	6.617	0.000	0.030
	Within groups	471.912	653	0.723			
	Total	486.259	656				

Source: Own elaboration

⁵ df = degrees of freedom

⁶ F = estimate of the population variance based on the existing variability between means of each group

⁷ p = Significance (P = o < 0.05)

⁸ η^2 = *Eta square* (effect size: 0.01 small, 0.06 medium, 0.14 big)

Table 7. Relative frequencies of responses for items with significance in the age variable

To become places of leisure that enhance enjoyment.					
	Strongly disagree	Quite a bit of disagreement	Neither agree nor disagree	Quite right	I totally agree
Young 18-29	4,5%	19,5%	31,2%	29,9%	13,0%
Adults 30-45	7,5%	20,1%	27,6%	30,6%	11,9%
Adults 46-64	11,4%	20,8%	25,0%	25,0%	12,3%
Older 65	20,3%	21,6%	24,8%	18,3%	3,9%

To defend the classic values of cultural heritage.					
	Strongly disagree	Quite a bit of disagreement	Neither agree nor disagree	Quite right	I totally agree
Young 18-29	0,6%	7,1%	14,9%	34,4%	40,9%
Adults 30-45	0,7%	3,0%	16,4%	22,4%	56,7%
Adults 46-64	0,8%	2,1%	9,7%	28,8%	56,8%
Older 65	0,7%	0,7%	5,2%	29,4%	56,2%

Include the gender perspective in their activities.					
	Strongly disagree	Quite a bit of disagreement	Neither agree nor disagree	Quite right	I totally agree
Young 18-29	3,2%	5,8%	20,1%	28,6%	35,1%
Adults 30-45	2,2%	6,7%	27,6%	31,3%	26,9%
Adults 46-64	6,4%	5,5%	28,4%	30,1%	20,8%
Older 65	3,9%	5,9%	24,2%	29,4%	16,3%

Increase the number of visitors to reach more people.					
	Strongly disagree	Quite a bit of disagreement	Neither agree nor disagree	Quite right	I totally agree
Young 18-29	5,2%	16,9%	33,1%	31,8%	10,4%
Adults 30-45	3,0%	11,2%	30,6%	30,6%	23,1%
Adults 46-64	6,8%	8,9%	27,1%	30,9%	22,5%
Older 65	1,3%	5,2%	26,1%	35,9%	19,6%

Source: Own elaboration

Table 8. ANOVA results of items with significance in crossing the importance given to visiting museums compared to other cultural practices variable and changes demanded

		Sum of Squares	df ⁹	Mean Square	F ¹⁰	p ¹¹	η^{212}
Increasing the number of visitors to reach more people	Between groups	14.006	2	7.003	6.175	0.002	0.019
	Within groups	728.071	642	1.134			
	Total	742.078	644				
Defending the classic values of cultural heritage	Between groups	27.185	2	13.592	19.422	0.000	0.056
	Within groups	457.692	654	0.700			
	Total	484.877	656				
Becoming places for the social inclusion of people with any kind of disability	Between groups	14.162	2	7.081	9.454	0.000	0.028
	Within groups	483.866	646	0.749			
	Total	498.028	648				
Proving enriching and memorable experiences	Between groups	6.227	2	3.114	6.833	0.001	0.020
	Within groups	302.564	664	0.456			
	Total	308.792	666				
Offering a vision that respects cultural diversity	Between groups	7.911	2	3.955	7.394	0.001	0.022
	Within groups	353.076	660	0.535			
	Total	360.986	662				

Source: Own elaboration

⁹ df = degrees of freedom

¹⁰ F = estimate of the population variance based on the existing variability between means of each group

¹¹ p = Significance (P = o < 0.05)

¹² η^2 = *Eta square* (effect size: 0.01 small, 0.06 medium, 0.14 big)

Table 9. Relative frequencies of responses for items with significance in the level of importance given to museums in comparison with other cultural practices variable

Increasing the number of visitors to reach more people					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
None or less importance	3.85%	11.54%	50.00%	26.92%	0.00%
The same importance	4.57%	14.72%	32.49%	27.92%	16.24%
A lot or much more importance	4.41%	8.37%	26.21%	34.36%	21.81%

Defending the classic values of cultural heritage					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
None or less importance	3.85%	11.54%	23.08%	30.77%	26.92%
The same importance	1.02%	3.05%	17.77%	35.53%	40.10%
A lot or much more importance	0.44%	2.64%	7.49%	25.99%	60.35%

Becoming spaces for the social inclusion of people with any kind of disability					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
None or less importance	11.54%	3.85%	23.08%	26.92%	26.92%
The same importance	1.02%	3.55%	18.27%	39.59%	32.49%
A lot or much more importance	0.66%	1.76%	14.54%	35.24%	44.27%

Providing enriching and memorable experiences					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
None or less importance	0%	3.85%	19.23%	42.31%	26.92%
The same importance	1.02%	0.51%	5.58%	52.79%	38.58%
A lot or much more importance	0.44%	0.66%	4.63%	42.95%	50.22%

Offering a vision that respects cultural diversity					
	(1) Strongly disagree	(2) Disagree	(3) Neither agree nor disagree	(4) Agree	(5) Totally agree
None or less importance	3.85%	3.85%	11.54%	38.46%	38.46%
The same importance	2.03%	1.02%	7.11%	37.56%	50.76%
A lot or much more importance	0.22%	0.88%	5.29%	31.50%	59.91%

Source: Own elaboration